

LimeSurvey – Colectica Integration

Author: Adam Zammit, ACSPRI adam.zammit@acsPRI.org.au

Document version: 1.0.0

Document date: 24 November 2023

1

2

Table of Contents

Background.....	3
Usage.....	3
Importing a question/questions – Step 1.....	4
Importing – Choose Import from Colectica plugin	5
Importing – Browse or search.....	6
Importing – Selecting questions and question group.....	7
Importing – imported question view.....	8
.....	8
Importing – preview question view	9
.....	9
Source URL	10

Background

LimeSurvey is the most popular open source web survey tool. It is used by institutions worldwide for collecting survey data. Colectica is a web based data and metadata archiving and publication tool. Colectica is used by institutions worldwide to publish their survey data in a structured format.

To enable the efficient reuse, referencing and documentation of high quality survey questions, the ImportQuestionFromColectica plugin was developed for LimeSurvey by ACSPRI as part of the IRISS project.

This plugin allows for administrators of LimeSurvey system to integrate with a Colectica repository, which allows LimeSurvey users to search or browse the repository in the LimeSurvey interface and create questions based on existing published survey questionnaires.

Usage

The ImportQuestionFromColectica plugin needs to be installed and configured by the LimeSurvey system administrator. Please follow the instructions in the README to do this.

Once the plugin is installed and configured, your users can follow the steps below to import questions from the Colectica repository.

Importing a question/questions – Step 1

Once installed, users can use the familiar LimeSurvey interface to add questions to their questionnaire. In the LimeSurvey question editor (structure) page, choose to add a new question by clicking the “Add question” button.

Importing – Choose Import from Colectica plugin

Next, click on the “Import from Colectica” button. If this button doesn’t appear, the plugin is not installed or configured correctly.

Importing – Browse or search

Here you have two options – either choose a questionnaire to browse the questions contained in it (1), or choose a search query and click on “Search Colectica” (2)

The screenshot shows the LimeSurvey interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The page title is "LimeSurvey — Mozilla Firefox". The browser address bar shows the URL "https://iriss-survey-demonstrator.acsPri.org.au/index". The page content is divided into a left sidebar and a main content area.

Left Sidebar:

- Settings (selected)
- Structure
- Survey settings
 - Overview
 - General settings
 - Text elements
 - Privacy policy
 - Theme options
 - Presentation
 - Participant settings
 - Notifications & data
 - Publication & access
 - Survey permissions
- Survey menu
 - Question list
 - Group list
 - Reorder questions & groups
 - Survey participants

Main Content Area:

- Buttons: Activate this survey, Preview survey, Tools, Export
- Section: Browse or Search Colectica for a question
- Section: Choose an Instrument to Browse (or search all below)
- List of questionnaires:
 1. AuSSA 2013 Questionnaire Wave 4
 2. AuSSA 2012 Wave 3/4
 3. AuSSA 2011 Questionnaire
 4. AuSSA B
 5. AuSSA 2009 A
 6. The Australian Survey of Social Attitudes
 7. The Australian Survey of Social Attitudes
 8. AuSSA 2022 Wave 4
 9. The Australian Survey of Social Attitudes
 10. Australian Census 2021
 11. AuSSA 2021 Wave 4
 12. AuSSA 2020 Wave 1
- Search query input field: health
- Search Colectica button

Two red boxes highlight the search query input field and the "Search Colectica" button.

Importing – Selecting questions and question group

First select the question or questions you wish to import by “ctrl” clicking the questions from the selection box. Then select which LimeSurvey group you want the questions in. Then click on the “Import question(s)” button. You can follow this import process multiple times, so you could choose to import sets of questions group by group, or import all required questions into one LimeSurvey group, and then use the LimeSurvey interface to rearrange them later.

The screenshot shows the LimeSurvey web interface in a Mozilla Firefox browser. The page title is "LimeSurvey — Mozilla Firefox". The browser address bar shows the URL "https://friss-survey-demonstrator.acspri.org.au/index.". The page header includes the LimeSurvey logo and navigation links: "Create survey", "Surveys", "Help", and a user profile "demo". The main content area is titled "Surveys → Colectica Test (513263)". Below this, there are tabs for "Settings" (selected) and "Structure". A top navigation bar contains buttons for "Activate this survey", "Preview survey", "Tools", and "Export". The "Import from Colectica" section features a link to "Return to Browse or Search Colectica for a question". Under "Select question(s) to import", a list of questions is shown, with "[A3] - Is it fair or unfair that people with higher incomes can afford better health care than people with lower incomes?" selected. Below this, the "Destination question group:" dropdown is set to "My first question group (ID:3)". An "Import question(s)" button is located at the bottom of the main content area. The left sidebar contains "Survey settings" (Overview, General settings, Text elements, Privacy policy, Theme options, Presentation, Participant settings, Notifications & data, Publication & access, Survey permissions) and "Survey menu" (Question list, Group list, Reorder questions & groups, Survey participants).

Importing – imported question view

Here is what the question looks like in LimeSurvey once imported. Note the “Question source URL” which is a reference to the question in the Colectica repository. Besides this source URL, the question is a regular LimeSurvey question object and can be edited / manipulated as normal in LimeSurvey.

Importing – preview question view

Here is what the question looks like previewed as a respondent once imported.

Source URL

The source URL refers back to the Colectia repository. This shows the complete reference cycle. The source URL will become part of the questionnaire metadata in LimeSurvey, and available to export as part of the LimeSurvey metadata file.

The screenshot shows a Mozilla Firefox browser window titled "D1 - MDR Staging". The address bar displays the URL: <https://mdr-staging.ausiriss.org.au/item/au.ada/229c7>. The page content includes a navigation bar with "MDR Staging", "Search", "Explore", and "Admin" links, along with a user profile for "ada@ada.edu.au". The main content area is titled "D1" and "AuSSA 2021 Wave 4". Below this, there is a "Question" section with the following details:

- Name:** D1
- Question Text:** Which of these best describes the North Pole?
- Instructions:** Please cross one box only
- Representation Type:** Code List
- Selection Style:** SelectOne
- Codes:**
 - Ice a few metres thick, floating over a deep ocean
 - Ice more than a kilometre thick, over land
 - A mainly rocky, mountainous landscape
 - Don't know

Below the question details, there is a "Usage" section showing "AuSSA 2021 Wave 4" and "134 questions before...".